

Effect of age of dhaincha on green and dry matter production and nitrogen added, Ludhiana, India.

Age of dhaincha (days)	Green matter (t/ha)	Dry matter (t/ha)	N added (kg/ha)
30	1.6	0.23	8.3
45	15.6	2.03	57.9
60	28.9	5.58	132.0

without dhaincha received basal P applied to rice. The dhaincha crops were buried one day before transplanting on 4 July.

Amount of green matter, dry matter, and N added increased with increasing dhaincha age (see table). In effect on yield, 60-day-old dhaincha alone was equal to 120 kg N/ha applied as urea; 45-day-old dhaincha was equal to 60 kg N/ha; 30-day-old dhaincha did not increase yield substantially (see figure). □

Effect of age of dhaincha green manure on N economy in rice. Ludhiana, India.

Improvement of crop stand in flooded rice fields

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Direct-seeded rice fields inundated soon after seeding — not infrequent in rainfed lowlands — show suboptimal stands. In controlled greenhouse investigations on improving the germination and crop stand for such situations, seeds soaked in a 1% solution of oxidizing chemicals such as hydrogen peroxide, potassium permanganate, or potassium dichromate for 24 hours were sown in moist soil and immediately flooded with 10, 20, and 40 cm water.

Seeds soaked in hydrogen peroxide and potassium permanganate showed higher germination (90-95%) under different floodwater depths. Seeds soaked in potassium dichromate had drastically reduced germination (40-50%). Seeds soaked in hydrogen peroxide produced vigorous seedlings that emerged rapidly, even from 40-cm-deep floodwater.

The study indicates the possibility of improving crop stands in direct-sown flooded ricefields by soaking the seed in hydrogen peroxide and potassium permanganate. □

Effect of azolla manuring with nitrogen fertilization

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The effect on rice grain yield of incorporating azolla into soil fertilized with nitrogen was studied in a field trial during 1979 rabi. The azolla levels tested were 0, 10, 20, and 30 t/ha; the N fertilizer levels, 0, 25, 50, 75, and 100 kg/ha; and the rice variety, ADT 31. Azolla levels formed the main treatment and nitrogen levels, the subtreatment. The treatments were repli-

cated twice. Azolla was incorporated 1 week before planting; nitrogen as urea was applied in one basal dose. P₂O₅ and K₂O at 50 kg/ha were applied just before planting. The addition of azolla at all levels and of nitrogen at all levels gave significantly higher yields (see table). □

Effect of azolla manuring along with nitrogen applications on grain yield of ADT 31, 1979 rabi, Aduthurai, India

N level (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)				Mean (N levels)
	with azolla incorporated at				
	0 t/ha	10 t/ha	20 t/ha	30 t/ha	
0	3.4	3.8	4.2	4.6	4.0
25	3.8	4.4	4.7	5.0	4.5
50	4.2	4.7	5.3	5.6	4.9
75	4.5	5.3	5.8	6.1	5.4
100	5.0	6.0	6.4	6.8	6.0
Mean (azolla levels)	4.2	4.8	5.3	5.4	
C.D.	Azolla levels 0.3		N levels 0.2		Interaction N.S.

Performance of rice transplanted under nonpuddled rainfed conditions

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Ragi *Eleusine coracana G.*, an important millet crop of Karnataka, is transplanted on the sides of ridges, then irrigated. A study was conducted to determine whether like ragi, rice could be transplanted under nonpuddled conditions and whether the subsequent rice crop could be grown under rainfed conditions, and given protective irrigation where necessary. A successful crop under these conditions would mean considerable water savings.

The test field was tilled during the early rains of the season. Ridges 20 cm

wide and furrows 30 cm wide were prepared. The field was irrigated to capacity. Thirty-day-old seedlings of 8 rice cultivars (see table) were transplanted on the sides of the ridges at 30- × 10-cm spacing with 2-3 seedlings/hill, in a randomized block design with 6 replications.

A basal application of 50 kg N/ha, 13 kg P/ha, and 30 kg K/ha was broadcast before ridges and furrows were prepared. Nitrogen at 25 kg/ha was applied in a band 5 cm away from planted rows at 20 and 45 days after transplanting. The crop was hand-weeded twice during

Performance of rice cultivars transplanted under nonpuddled conditions. Mandya, India, 1980 kharif (wet season).

Cultivar	Duration (days)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Rasi	125	4.4
IR20	150	3.7
Mangala	110	3.6
IRAT 2	150	3.5
Jaya	160	3.2
IRAT 10	144	3.2
Lagore	144	2.8
IRAT 13	116	2.0
CD (0.05)		0.11
CV (%)		29

the early stages of crop growth. A fair distribution of rains during the season made protective irrigation unnecessary.

Results indicated that, of the eight rices tested, Rasi recorded the significantly highest yield, followed by IR20 and Mangala (see table). These rices had early and good stand establishment, satisfactory canopy cover with high panicle number, and low spikelet sterility. The rice yields obtained were very competitive with those of ragi grown under similar conditions. □

Foliar spraying *Eichhornia* inoculum and incorporation of *Eichhornia* and *Ipomoea* green leaves as supplemental nitrogen sources

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The aquatic weeds *Eichhornia crassipes* and *Ipomoea carnea*, unlike conventional green leaf manures, are abundant. An experiment was conducted in a randomized block design, replicated four times, on the College Farm, Rajendranagar, in the 1977 wet season to determine the effect of *Eichhornia* inoculum spraying and *Eichhornia* and *Ipomoea* green leaf incorporation in the nitrogen economy of rice. One hundred milliliters of *Eichhornia* spray solution with a count of 23.1 × 10⁹/ml was diluted 10 times and sprayed in each 13.5-m² plot. In treatments with 2% urea spray, 1,000 ml of 2% urea solution was sprayed in each plot.

Grain yield was highest (4.1 t/ha) in the treatment with 100 kg N/ha (see table). It was on par with the yields in treatments that received 60 kg N/ha + *Eichhornia* leaves; 60 kg N/ha + *Ipomoea* leaves, and with 60 kg N/ha + 2% urea

Effect of *Eichhornia* inoculum spray and leaf incorporation of *Eichhornia* and *Ipomoea* with nitrogen application on rice yields. Rajendranagar, Hyderabad, India.

Treatment	Grain		Straw	
	Yield (t/ha)	Increase (%) over yield with 60 kg N/ha	Yield (t/ha)	Increase (%) over yield with 60 kg N/ha
100 kg N/ha	4.1	24	4.7	30
60 kg N/ha + <i>Ipomoea</i> leaf incorporation at 10 t/ha	3.9	18	4.2	17
60 kg N/ha + <i>Eichhornia</i> leaf incorporation at 10 t/ha	3.8	15	4.2	17
60 kg N/ha + 2% urea solution spray	3.8	15	3.8	6
60 kg N/ha + <i>Eichhornia</i> inoculum spray	3.7	12	3.5	97
60 kg N/ha + 2% urea spray + <i>Eichhornia</i> inoculum spray	3.5	6	3.9	8
60 kg N/ha	3.3	-	3.6	-
C.D. at 5%	0.4	-	0.4	-

spray. Yield differences between the treatment with 60 kg N/ha + 2% urea solution spray and that with 60 kg N/ha + *Eichhornia* inoculum spray were insignificant. That indicates a spraying of *Eichhornia* inoculum is as effective as 3 sprayings of 2% urea. *E. crassipes* and *I.*

carnea weeds, when used as green manure at 10 t/ha, provide supplementary 40 kg N/ha and increase rice grain yield. They do not proliferate in the field during succeeding seasons, however, if the leaves are properly incorporated before rice is planted. □

Fertilizer usage and productivity of aus, aman, and boro rice

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A study of 225 randomly selected farmers was conducted in Haringhata block, West Bengal, India, to determine the relationship between levels of fertilizer usage and rice yields during different seasons. Data for the preceding year were collected from January to March

1981.

Multiple regression analysis revealed that NPK levels used explained 73% of the variation in boro (dry season-winter rice) yields, 40% variation in aus (September, pre wet-season) yields, and 7% variation in aman (wet season) yields.